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ADAPTIVE PHYSICAL EDUCATION METHODS FOR THE BLIND AND BLIND IN MODERN SCHOOL CONDITIONS

Abstract. This article is dedicated to methods of adaptive physical education for children with visual impairments. The types and methods of physical exercises for solving the tasks of adaptive physical education are considered.

Keywords: adaptive physical education (APE), visual impairment, visually impaired, APE methods.

Introduction: The current decline in visual acuity in school-age children can be illustrated with the following example. In the specialized boarding school No. 10 "Nurli maskan" of the city of Nukus under the National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 274 school-age blind children are studying in the 2023-2024 academic year. The growth trend of children with visual impairments encourages the development of adaptive physical education in modern schools.

Adaptive physical education is a type of activity that allows a person with limited health to prepare for work and labor, to form elementary physical skills.

The adaptive physical training program is compiled taking into account individual approaches to load management, the learner's sensory capabilities, and emotional intensity. Based on this, there are various methods of education aimed at achieving different goals and an individual approach to each child, taking into account their health and developmental characteristics.

The verbal method is one of the typical methods of teaching children with visual impairments: discussion, description, explanation. The most common explanation, in which the student tries to understand and imagine a picture of the action, describes it, the teacher not only conveys the proposed material to the students, but also gives a spatial representation with objects and phenomena. Auditory perception helps children compare verbal explanations with things in reality that define them. Such practice with the help of auditory perception contributes to the creation of conditions for learning the definitions of more and more words and terms used in the assimilation of movements in adaptive physical training [1].

Various types of verbal explanations are used: accompanying explanation - brief comments and remarks that the teacher uses when performing exercises to improve the

perception of students, instruction - verbal explanation of the method of the studied action.

Also, the verbal method refers to the method of remote control, which involves remote regulation of the learner's actions using these commands, i.e., "turn right," "turn left," "three steps forward, right, left," etc. Sound information is often used by children with visual impairments. In most exercises, a sound arises in the process of interaction with an object, with the help of which you can form an understanding of the object. Thus, sound is used as a conditional signal [4].

The simulator method is based on the perception of information through the senses of the sensory organs in the learning process. This method teaches the child to feel muscles and joints when performing motor actions, and also allows transferring acquired knowledge into practical actions.

For example, if a child is offered to run after the teacher, catch up with him, then the trainee should be offered to run independently to pay attention to the movements of his arms and legs, to show muscle sensations, and then to achieve a repetition of the muscle forces he felt while running after the teacher.

The method of stimulating motor activity consists in rewarding children, for which it is necessary to allow them to experience the joy of movement, to help them get rid of a complex of irresponsibility, fear of emptiness, and self-doubt. Creating conditions for achieving success whenever possible [3].

In the training of visually impaired people, the visual method occupies a special place, which is one of the features of using teaching methods in the process of familiarization with objects and actions. In the process of examining sports objects, it is recommended to first divide the object into parts, set the goal: determine its shape, surface, quality, and then the student himself tries to fully perceive the object or actions. [5].

Certain requirements are imposed on visual aids, for example, large size of objects and saturation of colors. Red, yellow, green, orange colors are mainly used for the preparation of visual aids. For children to fully comprehend educational literature, demonstrations of movement actions and sports equipment are used. Visualization is always accompanied by oral explanation, which helps to prevent distortions in the representation of the subject and allows stimulating the mental activity of students.

Conclusion. When teaching children with visual impairments, as a rule, depending on the lesson objectives, some single method is used, and a multitude of complementary methods are used. A methodology that better ensures the development of children's motor activity is a priority. [1].

Thus, the study and analysis of methods of teaching blind and visually impaired people adaptive physical education contributes to the formation of proper development of children and the correction of their shortcomings.

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